

PRIVACY-PRESERVING COLLABORATIVE FILTERING: EVALUATING A MACHINE LEARNING RECOMMENDER SYSTEM IN A LARGE INTERCONNECTED ORGANIZATION

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Abstract

Collaborative filtering algorithms revolutionized the field of recommendation systems by taking advantage of user preferences and behaviors to provide personalized recommendations. Although CF is effective in providing accurate recommendations, it often requires access to users' personal data, raising privacy concerns. In response, researchers have proposed several privacy-preserving techniques to strike a balance between maintaining the accuracy of the recommendation and safeguarding user privacy. This research aims to evaluate the performance, effectiveness, and efficiency of privacy-preserving collaboration filtering techniques in a real-world setting, with a specific focus on CERN as the use case organization. The evaluation will assess the capability of collaborative filtering to protect user privacy while preserving recommendation accuracy within the context of CERN.

INTRODUCTION

The advent of Collaborative Filtering (CF) algorithms revolutionized the field of recommendation systems (RS) by leveraging user preferences and behaviors to provide personalized recommendations. While CF is effective in providing accurate recommendations, it often requires access to users' personal data, raising privacy concerns. This has led to privacy concerns becoming a crucial aspect in the design and implementation of CF algorithms for recommender systems. The widespread use of such systems in large interconnected organizations has additionally raised significant concerns regarding user and organisation privacy. As CF typically requires access to personal data, organizations must ensure that sensitive information remains protected. To address this challenge, the research community has proposed numerous privacy-preserving techniques in order to achieve a balance between maintaining the accuracy of the recommendation and protecting the privacy of the user [1, 2].

Although privacy-preserving CF has been widely studied, empirical evaluations in real-world situations, especially in large interconnected organisations, remain limited. This research aims to fill this gap by evaluating the performance, effectiveness, and efficiency of various privacy-preserving CF techniques in a real-world setting, with a specific focus on CERN as the use case organization. CERN, as a large interconnected organization with diverse user profiles and sensitive data, provides an ideal environment for evaluating

the capabilities of privacy-preserving CF algorithms. The evaluation will assess the capability of these techniques to protect user privacy while preserving recommendation accuracy within the context of CERN's organizational network. By conducting this evaluation, our aim is to provide valuable insights into the practical applicability and performance of privacy-preserving CF techniques, ultimately contributing to the development of privacy-aware recommender systems in organizational settings.

RELATED WORK

Researchers have proposed several privacy-preserving techniques to mitigate these risks while maintaining the effectiveness of recommendation algorithms. The need for privacy-preserving CF arises from the inherent trade-off between personalization and privacy. While maintaining the quality and accuracy of recommendations is essential, addressing privacy concerns in organizational settings is equally critical. Privacy-preserving recommender systems employ various strategies, such as privacy-preserving item-based CF, random perturbations, substitution encryption, secure multiparty computation, homomorphic encryption, and federated learning [3–5].

Evaluation of results produced by these methods in RS is a difficult task [6–8]. Two main types of recommendation evaluation metric suggested by the literature are statistical accuracy metrics (SAM) and decision support accuracy metrics (DSAM) [9, 10]. SAM such as Mean Absolute Error (MAE) evaluates the accuracy of a recommender system by comparing the prediction values with actual ratings for items that have both predictions and ratings [10, 11]. DSAM evaluate how effective a prediction engine is in helping a user select relevant items among available ones. The most common measures are precision and recall [9, 10]. Using proper model validation techniques assists in understanding models and estimating a model's performance. In the literature, multiple validation techniques exist, such as train/test split, k-fold cross-validation, nested cross-validation, McNemar's test, etc. The most common validation method used is train/test split in combination with k-fold cross-validation [12, 13].

Evaluating Privacy-Preserving CF (CF) techniques has been the focus of numerous studies in recent years. Research efforts have aimed to propose efficient and accurate algorithms that protect user privacy during the recommendation process [1]. Despite this, there is a lack of comprehen-

sive surveys in the field that explore privacy-preserving CF schemes from different perspectives [5].

CONCEPT

We will present a comprehensive evaluation of a collaborative filtering (CF) based recommender system (RS) integrated into an existing notification service at CERN. Using CF techniques, personalised recommendations will be provided to volunteer users of the service, enhancing their user experience. Importantly, the RS will be designed with a privacy-preserving approach, ensuring that Personal Identifiable Data (PII) are not used in the recommendation process.

To enhance the evaluation process, volunteers will be able to provide explicit feedback to the recommendations. Users will have the option to either approve the recommended item or ignore it, enabling the collection of valuable user feedback and assessment of the effectiveness of the CF-based RS. Additionally, the created date of each recommended item will be recorded to measure the time to user action, enabling the evaluation of the system's responsiveness and timeliness in delivering recommendations.

To ensure a comprehensive evaluation, various evaluation methods will be employed, including statistical accuracy metrics (SAM), such as mean absolute error (MAE) to assess recommendation accuracy, and decision support accuracy metrics (DSAM), such as precision and recall to evaluate the system's effectiveness in helping users select relevant items.

To follow the principles of privacy and openness, all data generated during the evaluation will be anonymised and made available as open source. This will allow other researchers to analyse the anonymised data and replicate the evaluation process.

The result of this research will be a comprehensive analysis and evaluation of a privacy-preserving CF-based RS where the data used in the evaluation will be open-sourced, ensuring reproducibility and facilitating further research.

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